

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16751429

A Study Of Multimodal Representation Of Cultural Diversity And National Unity In *My Super Family*

¹Fatima Ibrahim Gafai; ²Abdulahakim Saidu; ³Hauwa Yusuf Labo & ⁴Nasir Umar Abdullahi

Department of English and French, Humanities,
Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina, Nigeria

¹fatima.ibrahim@umyu.edu.ng; +2348132170746

²abdulahakim.saidu@umyu.edu.ng; +2348031383596

³hauwa.yusuf@umyu.edu.ng; +2348060820608

⁴nasir.umar@umyu.edu.ng; +2348035137323

ABSTRACT

This study examines *My Super Family*, a UNICEF-sponsored children's book, through the lens of Multimodal Discourse Analysis (MDA) to explore how text and images work together to promote cultural diversity, national unity, and peaceful coexistence in Nigeria. Drawing on Martinec and Salway's (2006) Multimodal Cohesion Framework, the analysis investigates the status, logico-semantic relations, and interpersonal meanings between verbal and visual elements, revealing how the book constructs a cohesive message of inclusion. Additionally, Halliday's (1978) Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) provides insight into how the ideational, interpersonal, and textual metafunctions of language contribute to identity formation and social bonding. Furthermore, Kress and van Leeuwen's (2006) Visual Social Semiotics is applied to analyze how representational, interactive, and compositional meanings visually reinforce Nigeria's multiculturalism. Findings suggest that *My Super Family* serves as both a literacy development tool and a sociopolitical narrative that aligns with global peace education discourses. The study highlights how multimodal strategies in children's literature reinforce social cohesion, bilingual literacy, and national identity construction in multilingual societies.

Keywords: Multimodal Representation; Cultural Diversity; National Unity, *My Super Family*

INTRODUCTION

Textbooks and story books targeting children play significant role in modeling the young minds. They foster cultural awareness and promote social cohesion. In the Nigerian multilingual and multicultural setting, children's books serve as powerful tools for teaching the early readers about national identity, diversity, and peaceful coexistence. A UNICEF-sponsored children's book titled *My Super Family* demonstrates this function by depicting an inclusive narrative that celebrates ethnic, linguistic, and religious diversity of the Nigerian society. This was majorly achieved through its multimodal design that combines text, illustrations, and layout which facilitates the construction of a cohesive message of unity despite differences. Previous studies focusing on how different semiotic resources contribute to meaning-making have examined the use of multimodal storytelling in educational context.

Studies such as Yassine (2014) and Purwaningtyas (2020) underscore the integration of visual and textual elements in EFL textbooks, emphasizing how images do more than complement texts but actively shape meaning-making. Similarly, Moftah, Hassan, and Ramadan (n.d.) analyze Disney-based children's stories, revealing how gaze, color, and composition contribute to the depiction of familial relationships. These insights align with the analysis of *My Super Family*, which employs multimodal strategies to reinforce themes of cultural diversity and national unity. Makinde and Odili

(2023) further support the role of multimodal analysis in understanding how primary school textbooks foster bilingual literacy and identity formation, a critical aspect also evident in *My Super Family*. Additionally, Wanselin, Danielsson, and Wikman (2021) highlight the pedagogical benefits of multimodal discourse in science education, reinforcing the idea that textual and visual interplay enhances comprehension. Collectively, these studies validate the significance of multimodal storytelling in educational contexts, echoing the focus of *My Super Family*, which integrates linguistic and visual semiotic resources to shape young readers' understanding of diversity and social cohesion in Nigeria. Thus, given Nigeria's complex sociocultural landscape, an analysis of *My Super Family* through a multimodal discourse lens could provide valuable insights into how children's literature can reinforce national unity while supporting early literacy and bilingualism.

Therefore, this study examines how *My Super Family* constructs cultural diversity, national unity, and social cohesion through its multimodal features. The study intends to investigate how semiotic resources such as text and visual are integrated to create meaning in the book. To achieve this, the study deploys Halliday's (1978); Kress & van Leeuwen's (2006) framework of social semiotics, Martinec & Salway's (2006) Multimodal Cohesion Theory and Kress and van Leeuwen's (2006) Visual Grammar. In essence, the study seeks to answer the questions: How do texts and images interact to reinforce themes of cultural diversity and unity in *My Super Family*? What multimodal strategies contribute to the book's cohesive structure and message? How does *My Super Family* reflect the Nigerian sociocultural landscape through its linguistic and visual choices? This will contribute to the growing body of work on multimodal discourse analysis (MDA), children's literature, and social cohesion in multilingual societies. This study will also be significant in explaining how children's books can serve as literacy development tools, sociopolitical texts and as well align with peace education initiatives. Therefore, educators, policymakers, and scholars interested in the role of multimodal storytelling in early childhood development, language education, and national identity construction might benefit from the findings of the study.

METHODOLOGY

This study deploys qualitative research design to carry out a Multimodal Discourse Analysis (MDA) by examining how *My Super Family* uses linguistic and visual elements to create meaning. MDA is particularly useful for understanding how multiple semiotic modes interact in a text (O'Halloran, 2011). The primary data for this study is *My Super Family*, analyzed in its entirety to examine the interplay between text and visuals. Key aspects include examining sentence structure, pronoun usage, and repetition and studying character positioning, symbolism, and interactive gaze and analyzing color and layout. The analysis follows certain steps. It begins by using Halliday's (1978) SFL to classify verbal elements into ideational, interpersonal, and textual metafunctions. It then proceeds to apply Kress & van Leeuwen's (2006) Visual Grammar to examine representational, interactive, and compositional meanings. Finally, the analysis deploys Martinec & Salway's (2006) framework to assess text-image relations and narrative cohesion.

Theoretical Framework

Considering the multimodal nature of the data under study, the research marries three frameworks in order to provide an exhaustive analysis. Halliday's (1978) Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) provides a foundation for understanding how language functions within *My Super Family* to construct meaning. The three metafunctions of language: ideational, interpersonal, and textual help in the analysis of the linguistic elements of the book. Ideational metafunction examines how the book represents Nigerian identity through processes of being (relational), doing (material), and thinking (mental). Interpersonal metafunction on the other hand, investigates how pronouns, direct address, and interactive images create engagement and foster a sense of inclusivity. Using textual metafunction, the study explores how repetition contributes to narrative cohesion. Similarly, Kress & van Leeuwen's (2006) Visual Social Semiotics is applied to analyze how representational, interactive, and compositional meanings visually reinforce Nigerian multiculturalism. Representational meaning examines how images construct Nigerian ethnic, linguistic, and religious diversity. Interactive meaning assesses the role of gaze, social distance, and reader engagement in reinforcing inclusivity. Compositional meaning analyzes the arrangement of characters, symbols, and cultural artifacts to

highlight unity. Furthermore, Martinec and Salway's (2006) framework helps in evaluating how text and images interact to create cohesive meaning. Status (Equal or Unequal Relationship) determines whether text elaborates on or extends the meaning of the images. Logico-semantic relations explore how images expand or project verbal meanings. Interpersonal cohesion assesses how layout and color choices influence reader interpretation.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Linguistic Strategies in Constructing National Identity

Use of First-Person Narration to Create Personal Engagement

This first sentence is used to establish a personal bond between Ade, the narrator and the reader through the use of first-person narration. Likewise, by narrating the story from Ade's perspective, the book constructs a sense of intimacy and relationship, especially for young readers. Moreover, the use of "I" on page 1, "My name is Ade and I have a super family", and other places, stresses Ade's personal ownership of her family's story. It also makes the narrative more engaging and emotionally resonant. In addition, the first person narrative style used in the book, demonstrates a consistent narrative voice that guides reader through the story. For example, on page 12 Ade recounts her grandfather's words: "Grandpa says our family tells the true story of Nigeria". This personal reflection helps in structuring the narrative, tying together the various elements of Ade's family life and connecting them to the broader theme of national identity.

Figure 1: Use of First-Person Narration to Create Personal Engagement

Repetition of "My Super Family" as a Unifying Theme

The phrase, "My Super Family" is repeatedly used to serve as a thematic refrain that buttresses the primary message of unity and diversity. It is intentionally repeated on page (1,4,6,12,16). Each repetition reinforces Ade's pride in her family and, by extension, in Nigeria's multicultural identity. For example, on page 14, Ade asserts, "We love, respect, and protect each other," followed the refrain "My Super Family" on page 16. These reoccurrences construct a sense of rhythm and familiarity, which is particularly effective for young readers, encouraging them to internalize the message of pride in diversity.

We love, respect and protect each other.

I love my super family.

Figure 2: Repetition of “My Super Family” as a Unifying Theme

Furthermore, the repetition of “My Super Family” also acts as a cohesive device, linking different parts of the narrative. For example, the phrase is intangibly used on page 9 to introduce a section about the distinct food of the family. At the same time, it is deployed on page 10 to introduce a discussion of cultural clothing. Hence, this repetition helps in structuring the narrative and insuring that the theme of unity in diversity stands as the most dominant throughout the book.

Some foods look different but they all taste yummy.

We all look good in our different cultural clothes.

Figure 3: Repetition of intangible “My Super Family” phrase as a cohesive device

Promotion of Bilingual Literacy through Language Choices

So many Nigerian languages have been recognized in the book, depicting the linguistic diversity of the country. For instance, Ade lists greetings in different languages on page 4: “*Sannu da zuwa*” (Hausa), “*Nnoo*” (Igbo), “*Ajooma*” (Ibibio), “*Ibolachi*” (Igala), “*E ku abo*” (Yoruba), and “*Ob’okhian*” (Edo). This linguistics diversity reflects the reality of Nigeria’s multilingual society and validates the use of indigenous languages.

Figure 4: Bilingual Literacy through Language Choices

These multiple languages have been included to create an inclusive environment for target audience from different linguistic backgrounds. Ade says, on page 5, “I am proud to speak Yoruba and Igbo very well”. Here, Ade is proud to be bilingual courtesy of the heterogenic nature of her family. Again, saying it with pride would encourage readers to value linguistic diversity. Therefore, the multilingual elements are seamlessly integrated into the text and often followed by English translations. For example, the greetings on page 4 are followed by the English word “Welcome,” to ensure that the narrative remains accessible to all and sundry. This integration of languages enhances the richness and cultural authenticity to the text while maintaining coherence.

To this end, it is pertinent to emphasize that First-person narration, in *My Super Family*, creates a personal and engaging narrative voice, fostering empathy and connection with the reader. This could be found on page, 1,2, and 11 where Ade directly addresses the reader. On the other hand, the incessant repetition of “My Super Family” reinforces the central theme of unity in diversity and provides structural cohesion to the narrative (e.g., pp. 1, 4, 6, 12, 16). Consequently, the multilingual portrayal promotes bilingual literacy and reflects Nigeria’s linguistic diversity, validating the use of indigenous languages and fostering inclusivity (e.g., pp. 4, 5). These techniques are made to work together to weave a narrative that celebrates cultural diversity and concurrently promote a unified national identity. Thus, the book efficiently uses language as a tool of interaction with young readers to validate their cultural backgrounds, and encourage pride in Nigeria’s diverse cultural heritage.

5.1 Visual Strategies in Representing Diversity

Clothing, Food, and Celebrations as Cultural Markers of Nigerian Identity

The illustrations in *My Super Family* use clothing, food, and celebrations as **cultural markers** to visually represent Nigeria’s diversity. Clothing is deployed as a cultural marker. For example, On page 10, the characters are depicted wearing traditional Nigerian attire, such as Yoruba *agbada*, Igbo *isiagu*, and Hausa *babban riga*. These cultural outfits construct a unique symbolism that represents the distinct ethnic identities within Ade’s family. Likewise, the intricate patterns of the clothing with vibrant colors visually emphasize the beauty and uniqueness of each culture.

Similarly, on page 8, the illustrations show a variety of Nigerian dishes, such as *jollof rice*, *pounded yam*, and *tuwo*. These foods are not only visually appealing but also serve as symbols of cultural heritage. The depiction of food from different ethnic groups reinforces the theme of unity in diversity, as the family enjoys meals together despite their cultural differences. Furthermore, on page 7, the illustrations depict the family celebrating both Christmas and Sallah, two major religious festivals in Nigeria. The visual representation of these celebrations highlights the coexistence of Christianity and Islam in Nigerian society. The festive atmosphere, with decorations, gifts, and shared meals, underscores the joy and harmony that come from embracing cultural and religious diversity.

Figure 5: Cultural Markers of Nigerian Identity

Gaze and Engagement

The use of gaze and character positioning in the illustrations plays a crucial role in engaging the reader and fostering a sense of participation. For example, on page 1, Ade is depicted looking directly at the reader with a smile, creating a sense of connection and inviting the reader into her world. This demand image (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2006) establishes a personal relationship between Ade and the reader, making the narrative more engaging and inviting.

Figure 6: Demand image

However, on page 12, the grandfather is shown looking at Ade while speaking, rather than at the reader. This offer image shifts the focus to the interaction between the characters, allowing the reader to observe the family dynamics and reflect on the grandfather's message about Nigeria's diversity.

Figure 7: Offer image

In terms of character positioning, throughout the book, characters are often positioned in groups, emphasizing their togetherness and unity. For example, on page 14, the family is shown standing close together, holding hands, and smiling. This visual arrangement reinforces the theme of love and mutual respect, while also inviting the reader to feel part of the family's bond.

Figure 8: Character positioning

Representations of Christianity and Islam in Shared Celebrations

The illustrations in *My Super Family* use compositional strategies to visually represent religious inclusivity through shared celebrations. For example: On page 7, the family is depicted celebrating both Christmas and Sallah together. The illustrations show a Christmas tree alongside a crescent moon and star, symbolizing Islam. This visual juxtaposition highlights the coexistence of Christianity and Islam in Ade's family and, by extension, in Nigerian society. The shared joy and participation in both festivals emphasize the theme of religious harmony. Likewise, the use of religious symbols, such as the cross and the crescent moon, is subtle but significant. These symbols are integrated into the illustrations in a way that respects both religions without privileging one over the other. For example, on page 6, the family is shown together, with some members wearing hijabs and others wearing Western-style clothing, visually representing the blending of religious and cultural identities. Moreover, the use of vibrant colors and balanced compositions in the illustrations further reinforces the theme of inclusivity. For instance, on page 7, the warm colors and festive decorations create a sense of unity and celebration, while the balanced layout ensures that both Christmas and Sallah are given equal visual prominence.

Therefore, the visual strategies use in representing diversities in my *Super Family* include clothing, food, and celebrations which serve as powerful visual markers of Nigeria's cultural diversity, emphasizing the beauty and richness of its ethnic and religious traditions as in page 8, 10, 7. In the same vein, gaze and engagement strategies, such as direct and indirect gaze, along with character positioning, create a sense of connection and participation, drawing the reader into the narrative (e.g., pp. 1, 12, 14). On the other hand, religious inclusivity is visually represented through shared celebrations, symbolic elements, and balanced compositions, highlighting the coexistence of Christianity and Islam in Nigerian society (e.g., pp. 6, 7). These visual strategies work together to reinforce the book's themes of cultural diversity, national unity, and peaceful coexistence. The illustrations not only complement the text but also deepen the reader's understanding of Nigeria's multicultural identity.

Text-Image Relations

In relation to text-image relations, the illustrations often extend the meaning of the text by providing additional details that are not explicitly stated in the words. For example: On page 2, the text states, "My daddy is Yoruba and my mummy is Igbo." The accompanying illustration shows Ade's parents dressed in traditional Yoruba and Igbo attire. The father wears a Yoruba *agbada*, while the mother wears an Igbo *gele and wrapper*. This visual extension helps young readers understand the cultural significance of the text by showing the distinct ethnic identities of Ade's parents. Similarly, on page 8,

the text mentions, “We eat tasty foods from our different cultures.” The illustration shows a table filled with dishes like *jollof rice*, *pounded yam*, and *tuwo*. This visual extension provides a vivid depiction of the foods described, allowing readers to see the diversity of Nigerian cuisine.

Moreso, the illustrations frequently reinforce the text by visually echoing its message. For example: On page 14, the text states, “We love, respect, and protect each other.” The illustration shows the family members holding hands and smiling, visually reinforcing the message of unity and mutual care. The image strengthens the emotional impact of the text by showing the family’s bond in a tangible way. Further, on page 10, the text mentions, “We come together to celebrate every Sallah and Christmas.” The illustration shows the family celebrating both festivals, with a Christmas tree and a crescent moon symbolizing Islam. This visual reinforcement highlights the coexistence of Christianity and Islam in the family. But, in some cases, the text and images complement each other by providing different but related information. For example: On page 4, the text lists greetings in various Nigerian languages (“*Sanu da zuwâ*,” “*Nnoo*,” etc.), while the illustration shows Ade’s extended family members smiling and waving. The text provides linguistic diversity, while the image complements it by showing the warmth and inclusivity of the family.

2. Color and Layout

The use of vibrant colors throughout the book creates a sense of energy and celebration, reflecting the richness of Nigerian culture. For example: On page 10, the characters are depicted wearing brightly colored traditional attire, such as red, blue, and yellow *agbada* and *gele*. These colors not only highlight the beauty of the clothing but also symbolize the vibrancy of Nigeria’s cultural diversity. On page 7, the festive colors of Christmas (red, green, and gold) and Sallah (white and silver) are blended harmoniously in the illustrations, visually representing the coexistence of different religious traditions.

The compositional layout of the illustrations plays a key role in creating harmony between diverse elements. For example: On page 14, the family is depicted in a circular formation, holding hands and smiling. This circular layout symbolizes unity and equality, as no single family member is given more prominence than the others. The balanced composition reinforces the message of mutual respect and love. On page 8, the table filled with diverse foods is centrally positioned, drawing the reader’s attention to the shared act of eating. The layout emphasizes the idea that despite their differences, the family comes together to enjoy a common meal.

Symbolic Representations

The act of eating together is a powerful symbol of unity in the book. For example: On page 8, the text states, “We eat tasty foods from our different cultures,” and the illustration shows the family gathered around a table, sharing a meal. This everyday activity symbolizes the family’s ability to embrace their differences while coming together as one. The shared meal becomes a metaphor for national unity, where diverse cultures coexist harmoniously. Again, playing together symbolically represent unity. On page 11, the text mentions, “We talk, laugh, and have a happy time,” and the illustration shows the family playing together outdoors. This depiction of playfulness and joy symbolizes the happiness that comes from embracing diversity and fostering strong familial bonds. The act of playing together reinforces the idea that unity is not just about coexistence but also about shared joy and mutual support. In addition, celebrating together is another symbol of unity. On page 10 for instance, the family’s participation in both Christmas and Sallah celebrations symbolizes religious inclusivity. The illustrations show the family decorating a Christmas tree and sharing gifts, alongside scenes of Sallah celebrations. These shared activities highlight the family’s ability to honor and celebrate different religious traditions, symbolizing the broader theme of national unity in diversity.

Consequently, as detailed in this section, text-image relations enhance the narrative by extending, reinforcing, or complementing the text, creating a cohesive and multi-layered message of unity in diversity (e.g., pp. 2, 8, 14). Color and layout on the other hand, create visual harmony, using vibrant colors and balanced compositions to reflect the beauty and balance of Nigeria’s multicultural identity (e.g., pp. 7, 10, 14). Also, symbolic representations of everyday activities, such as eating, playing, and celebrating, serve as powerful metaphors for unity, emphasizing the joy and strength that come from embracing diversity (e.g., pp. 8, 11, 7). Thus, these multimodal strategies work together to create a rich and cohesive narrative that promotes cultural diversity, national unity, and peaceful coexistence.

The interplay between text and images, combined with symbolic representations, ensures that the book's message is both visually and emotionally impactful.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated how *My Super Family* employs multimodal strategies to construct a narrative of cultural diversity and national unity. The integration of linguistic and visual elements, analyzed through Social Semiotics, Visual Grammar, and Multimodal Cohesion Theory, reveals that the book serves both as a literacy development tool and a sociopolitical text promoting inclusivity in Nigeria. This research expands existing scholarship on multimodal discourse analysis by applying a combination of theories to analyze children's literature. It also contributes to studies on bilingual literacy, peace education, and national identity formation. Therefore, the study highlights the importance of publishing multicultural children's literature to promote national cohesion. It encourages further exploration of multimodal storytelling in African children's books. Based on the limitations of the current study, the researchers suggest that future investigations could focus on comparative analysis with similar books from other cultural contexts. Another gap for future study is reader-response studies to assess how children interpret multimodal elements. Likewise, investigating the impact of multimodal storytelling on early literacy development could be an illuminating study. To this end, this study has established the significance of multimodal storytelling in shaping young readers' understanding of diversity, unity, and social inclusion.

REFERENCES

- Halliday, M. A. K. (1978). *Language as social semiotic: The social interpretation of language and meaning*. Edward Arnold.
- Kress, G., & van Leeuwen, T. (2006). *Reading images: The grammar of visual design* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Makinde, P. O., & Odili, P. A. (2023). *A social semiotic analysis of selected basic pupils' English textbooks in Awka*.
- Martinec, R., & Salway, A. (2006). A system for image-text relations in new (and old) media. *Visual Communication*, 5(3), 337–371. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1470357206068468>
- Moftah, A. F. A. H., Hassan, H. M., & Ramadan, O. R. M. (n.d.). *Depiction of the family's relationships in selected children's short stories: A multimodal analysis*.
- O'Halloran, K. L. (2011). Multimodal discourse analysis. In K. Hyland & B. Paltridge (Eds.), *The Continuum companion to discourse analysis* (pp. 120–137). Continuum.
- Purwaningtyas, T. (2020). *Didactic symbol of visual images in EFL textbook: Multimodal critical discourse analysis*.
- Wanselin, H., Danielsson, K., & Wikman, S. (2021). *Analysing multimodal texts in science—a social semiotic perspective*.
- Yassine, S. (2014). *Multimodal design of EFL textbooks: A social semiotic multimodal approach*.